

How to market early-stage startups nationally in Australia

Report by coursework students of UTS 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, 2022 cohort

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Foreword

This report is part of a series of student-generated series about entrepreneurial ecosystems. Each report is a derivative of their coursework. The subject, 94663 Navigating Entrepreneurial Ecosystems and Initiating Change, is a core subject in the Diploma in Innovation at TD School and a popular elective across other UTS degree programs. The subject was piloted as part of the launch for the Sydney School of Entrepreneurship in 2017¹ and draws on prior research and engagement projects to visualise entrepreneurial ecosystems.²

The subject runs for three weeks in July, during which teams of students are tasked with defining and exploring an entrepreneurial ecosystem, understanding its history and visualising its current state. Based on that knowledge, they then develop proposals to advance the ecosystem.

The reports reflect the work that was presented publicly to invited guests and stakeholders in the subject, as well as members of the public who joined the presentations via the publicly available event page.

General Methodology

In partnership with Investment NSW (e.g., Sydney Startup Hub) and Spark Festival, the cohort of ~45 students was given the option to focus on Sydney CBD, Western Sydney, or Nationally. Additionally, one team was based overseas and was free to choose an international city to navigate.

The general method of this study follows our own method of evaluating ecosystems that has evolved over years of experience, in consultation with an Australian wide network of ecosystem researchers. While our process is not yet well documented, it is entirely consistent with the 2018 guide produced by the German Society for International Collaboration,³ promoted by the Aspen Network of Development Entrepreneurs (ANDE).

In addition to learning about ecosystems, teams engaged with ecosystems in authentic and immersive learning experiences. Stakeholder types and specific stakeholders in the ecosystem were identified based on Stam's seminal (2015) review of ecosystem factors. Insights about the ecosystem were generated by analysing desktop reports and media interviews involved those stakeholders. Where possible, teams conducted their own interviews of key stakeholders, including asking them about the ecosystem's history, evolution and critical events, and their vision for how it may evolve further. By synthesising such reports and interviews from multiple stakeholders, teams developed a composite story of the ecosystem's evolution, visualised its current state and identified specific opportunities for change. These reports present this analysis of the ecosystems' evolution as well as the team's proposal for specific interventions by which to intentionally advance the ecosystem in a specific direction.

The method can be tailored to specific ecosystems, ranging from rural communities through to internationally acclaimed innovation precincts. The breadth of Stam's framework and this method enables pushing back against the myth that innovation and entrepreneurship is primarily the domain of high-tech startups and VCs. While they do play a very important role, they are not the only organisations that matter to create economic growth (Brown & Mason, 2017; Spigel et al., 2020).

Field research for coursework follows the same principles as field research for academic purposes. As a result, the students' work mirrored the process of ecosystem research conducted by Martin Bliemel, for which he has ethics approval (HREC# ETH18-3020).

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¹ Bliemel, M., Schweitzer, J., Roy, G., Keitel, A., Nicolas, L., Miles, M., ... & Griffith, S. (2019, November). Herding cats to co-create cross-university courses in record time. *UIIN University-Industry Interaction Conference 2019*. University Industry Innovation Network.

² Bliemel, M. (2019). University-based entrepreneurial ecosystems and their visualisations. *University-Industry Innovation Magazine*.

³ <https://www.goethe.de/resources/files/pdf197/5.-guide-for-mapping-the-entrepreneurial-ecosystem.pdf>

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1 Evolution of the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

1.1 Definition

As a whole, the entrepreneurial ecosystem within Australia was largely non-existent until the introduction of policy in the 1980's to support entrepreneurship and funding and it wasn't until the mid 2000's that a somewhat thriving ecosystem with adequate infrastructure began to take shape at a much faster rate. Under our scope, the entrepreneurial ecosystem pertaining specifically to generating market exposure, growth and ultimately, customer acquisition for early-stage start-ups is also a more recent phenomenon. The ubiquity of the internet ultimately democratised the ability for early-stage start-ups to market at a national scale, representing a crucial inflexion point for this ecosystem.

1.2 2010s in cafes and social gatherings (Social gatherings to online hubs growth)

The Australian Start-up ecosystem started within Cafes, entrepreneurs with ideas came together to network because there was no "Silicon Valley" within Australia. While not reaching the same heights of Silicon Valley, there has been impressive growth over the last 20 years for Sydney start-ups, with fishburners being founded in 2011. Sydney has become so popular that it's becoming the place to network. In fact, both national and foreign entrepreneurs are moving to Sydney to take advantage of this (Agrawal, 2016). This is dampening the start-up spheres in other states by filtering talent to Sydney, but overall, all growth within Sydney bolsters the Australian start-up community.

Covid 19 has also made a drastic change to the way entrepreneur's network. Zoom meetings and online forums have seen a spike in usage and many start-up spheres are accommodating this change in work habit (Guckenbiehl, 2022). Cafes and Networking events have been substituted by providing online means of transferring and delivering communication, with some entrepreneurs opting to watch recorded lectures and events as opposed to attending.

1.3 Accelerators and incubators

Accelerators and incubators are a crucial part of a robust entrepreneurial ecosystem, and the prevalence of these organisations can provide a clear indicator of the state of the ecosystem as a whole. Reflective of Australia's entrepreneurial and start-up ecosystem, both accelerators and incubators have only existed in recent history. Incubators have existed within Australia since the 1980's, initially focusing upon regional commercial growth and small to medium enterprises (Bliemel et al., 2016), differing somewhat from the mainstream notion of an incubator today.

Accelerators have only emerged much more recently, first emerging in the mid 2000's due to a combination of government intervention and a growth in angel investors looking for new ventures (Bliemel & Flores, 2013). However, due to the rapid evolution of Australia's entrepreneurial ecosystem, as of 2019 there was a total of around 172 accelerator programs across the country (Statista, 2019). This is reflective of the inflection point of this ecosystem and the rapid growth and development that has occurred within the last 10-15 years.

1.4 Funds and grants

Australia is considered as one of the greatest start-up hubs (Agrawal, 2016). Countering the trends in many European countries, The Australian government have slowly increased their investment into the start-up space. Australian entrepreneurs have access to a over 600 grants and programs due to governmental assistance, with an increasing amount of support going to minorities and technological based sectors within the last 10 years.

There are currently 386 grant funds for businesses with less than a 2-year life span. These grants can assist anything from regional expansion to research and development. The Australian Government has implemented an online tool used to help entrepreneurs to find grants that they are eligible for. However,

due to the impact of COVID-19, there has been a shift in focus from start-up grants to COVID-19 grants. Early-stage start-ups are beginning to lose out.

1.5 Regional

While the major cities of Australia were growing and gaining traction with start-ups and entrepreneurialism in the early 2010's, regional areas of Australia were left till later to be supported. While there were grants and funding from the Australian government for innovation and entrepreneurship, there was a severe lack in the entrepreneurial ecosystems support in these regional areas. However, there were some people who saw the lack of support and took it into their own hands to develop the start-up ecosystem in Australia. One of the major milestones to minimise this gap was the initiative of Troy Haines, founder of 'theSpace'. He founded the start-up in 2012 with the hope of being able to build the entrepreneurial ecosystem within his own regional town, Cairns. Within about four years 'theSpace' was creating small regional ecosystems around Queensland, and looking to help those in other regional areas across Australia. Through support like 'theSpace' there has been a growing of "soft infrastructure, meaning developing connections through the ecosystem and building a culture of entrepreneurship." (Haines, 2016) At this point there are support systems for regional entrepreneurs, but there is still a long way to go to give them the best opportunities to grow and thrive.

1.6 Conclusion

In conclusion, the early-stage start-up entrepreneurial ecosystem has evolved rapidly over the last 20 years. Now, more than ever before there is a distinct understanding of the need for infrastructure to support founders in the initial stages of business as they look to gain market exposure and growth. The next stage of evolution will ultimately focus upon developing the infrastructure to sufficiently support and encourage regional entrepreneurs and founders from minority groups.

2 Ecosystem Mapping

2.1 The Map

Figure 1: Australia's National Entrepreneurial Ecosystem

2.2 Explanation of the metaphor

Explanation of the metaphor

We visualised the Entrepreneurial Ecosystem of early-stage startups as a marine ecosystem, where different depths of the sea correspond to different stages of the startup: ideation, realisation, conversion and scale.

In the metaphor, the startup is a scuba diver, who will start from the surface, an idea, and will dive deeper as the business idea develops; the diver will also move across the levels whenever there's a need to pivot from the initial journey, and will always refer to the sandy coast, which represents the community and network around the startup.

The “fluidity” of the ecosystem

The stakeholders in the ecosystem of early-stage startups present many similarities with the living elements of a marine ecosystem.

Firstly, like the currents and the microorganisms in the sea, many actors will be present at any stage of a startup: competitors will always be a relevant source of inspiration, university programs can provide skills and knowledge to young visionaries as well as to relatively seasoned entrepreneurs; government websites and support for SMEs will be a reliable source of information at every stage of the business.

Secondly, certain deep ocean creatures will not rise to the surface: likewise, many angel investors and VC will only consider funding startups with existing traction and conversion and are unapproachable for those who are still working on their business idea.

How startups move across their EE

Inexperienced divers, like people with an entrepreneurial idea, will start from the coast and from the surface: finding opportunities and needs in their everyday life is the best way for startups to become creative and find an idea they want to elaborate.

The deeper they get into their ideas, maybe with discovery interviews, studies on market fit and traction, the more their ecosystem will expand.

A crucial aspect of the EE of early-stage startups is how they can move around, back and forth, according to their needs: after going through a few incubators and/or accelerators, or after testing a first MVP, they might have to pivot from the initial idea, go back to the ideation phase and get ready to immerse again in networking, applying for new programs and joining new co-working spaces.

Importance of Connections

The great element of the EE of early-stage startups is how different actors often work together in supporting startups in their journey into different phases.

The University of Technology of Sydney, for example, is an institution that provides training and mentoring, but it also collaborates with many other actors who have different functions; in one week we had the chance to get in contact with Spark Festival, Sydney Startup Hub, and UTS Startups. Among these, Sydney Startup Hub puts startups in contact with accelerator and incubator programs, pitch nights, government initiatives and investors.

Therefore, it is important that early-stage startups embrace the rich and broad range on interconnections that they will create with other startups, that other actors have and from which they can benefit, and from the support that this will give them while going back and forth in their entrepreneurial journey.

3 Leverage Proposal

AusHorizons believes that the major hinderance for early-stage start-ups trying to undergo a successful national marketing campaign is the lack of entrepreneurial knowledge and networks. Through our interviews and research, we conclude that the current entrepreneurial ecosystem is not made aware to new entrepreneurs, and so less knowledgeable entrepreneurs lose out on potential opportunities, especially those in regional areas.

In 10 years', we believe this gap will be filled. AusHorizons vision is that the new entrepreneurial ecosystem will enable entrepreneurs to seek guidance with all relevant stakeholders and assist in the possible paths through the ecosystem. With healthier feedback loops, entrepreneurs will have a higher awareness of the ecosystem in which they partake, which bolsters networking opportunities for co-founders and talent. In addition to knowledge, there will be a better-connected entrepreneur ecosystem for regional areas to be able to collaborate and market start-ups to urban stakeholders. With a few levers in place, Early-stage start-ups marketing efforts can thrive through approachable infrastructure and frameworks.

3.1 Lever 1: Hybrid Ecosystem Education

Although government intervention and interaction within the free market should be somewhat limited and not overbearing upon the market, a very intentional and pragmatic approach to what is needed can have a profound effect upon a growing ecosystem such as the one we are exploring. Thus, the primary stakeholder who is in the position to have a centralised impact upon our ecosystem is government, however, in conjunction with the other stakeholders in the ecosystem rather than acting in sole independence.

In our exploration of this ecosystem, we found that founders typically have a lack of understanding of the context in which they are looking to enter or currently entering in the initial stages of ideation, validation and development. Context is a crucial starting point when you are looking to disrupt and or thrive within an ecosystem. As Australia's national entrepreneurial ecosystem continues to evolve and become increasingly robust, it is critical that stakeholders and in particular, founders looking to enter this ecosystem are aware of the major actors, stakeholders, firms and organisations that exist within the ecosystem and which actors are the most pertinent to their developing founder journey.

Our lever is to provide new or prospective founders with a hybrid, educational experience consisting of a physical kit of resources and access to an online portal and stakeholder led bootcamp. The physical resources will consist of a snapshot of the current ecosystem and all of the key stakeholders within the ecosystem, information on how to build a successful start-up from ideation and validation to execution and growth, access to government grants and funding and general advice and guidance. It will also provide information on the various accelerators, incubators and programs available and the differences and strengths of each, information on obtaining angel investment, financing and venture capital, and the key firms that solely work with founders, start-ups and innovative companies in order to generate market exposure, customer acquisition and overall growth. Although there is a tendency for resources to only exist online for convenience and resources sake, the physical nature of these resources is crucial to providing a tactile, tangible experience, inviting the founder to experience and begin to feel like a part of the ecosystem rather than simply an onlooker.

The online portal will build upon current governmental resources and programs but centralising and forming a singular point of access for early-stage founders that are looking to reach a national market. It will breakdown information and give direction for state and region-specific information, but the primary focus will be on the national scope of the ecosystem. There will be further information regarding everything that is outlined in the physical kit along with additional resources. There will be an initial bootcamp course that is created in conjunction with major accelerators and incubators throughout the country culminating to an apex in which the founder is invited to virtually map out the ecosystem as it pertains to them and their journey, based upon what they have learnt and additional research that is specific to their sector of the market and overarching mission and goal.

In terms of when this could be done, an initial testing could be conducted within about 6 months and an official rollout within 12-18 months.

3.2 Lever 2: Free 1-Off Start-Up Consultation

Early-stage start-ups are finding it difficult to market nationally, our interviews suggest that a major problem for early-stage entrepreneurs is the lack of knowledge and subsequent direction. The start-up space has a steep learning curve, and many entrepreneurs don't know where to go to acquire knowledge and are often intimidated by incubators and start-up groups. Furthermore, despite the increase in generous governments grants throughout the years, we've found that many entrepreneurs lack the knowledge to apply.

"The hardest step was the first"- Adam Wearne, Co-founder of Automated Garden Care

To put it briefly, we've discovered that many entrepreneurs skip out on crucial networking by failing to incorporate start-up spaces into their entrepreneurial journey. With a lack of time and knowledge, they opt to create and market their idea without assistance. We propose that the root problem with the difficulties in marketing for early-stage start-ups is that new entrepreneurs don't bother with spending resources and time figuring out how to integrate with their entrepreneurial ecosystem, putting them at a disadvantage when it comes time to market their idea.

We propose a free 1-off start-up consultation provided by the government.

This consultation is intended to break the barrier of entry for new entrepreneurs. We suggest that the government promote consultations sessions, in which entrepreneurs are allocated consultants based on the industry they intend to enter. The aim is a cultural shift in the mainstream, that the first touch point for all aspiring entrepreneurs should be this consultation. This lever:

- Increases knowledge in a specific sector
- Provides networking opportunities
- Increases emotional support and motivation as being led in the right direction can help entrepreneurs with the fear of the unknown.
- Find talent and skill sets for entrepreneurs.
- Redefine and consult on legal boundaries.

We believe that Governments should intervene in the ecosystem in the ideation/early creation phase while early entrepreneurs are developing their mindset and networks. This lever spearheads information flow and promotes positive feedback loops by connecting entrepreneurs to individuals who can assist them further.

We recommend that Government agencies shift a portion of their funding from grants to accommodate these free consultations. The broader scale of these consultations will bring more talent into the Australian start-up ecosystem. Similar consultations are often provided to start-ups by their incubators and start-up hubs, this consultation however is more widely available.

3.3 Lever 3: National not-for-profit helping to build and connect EE's

The key stakeholders that are in a position to intervene with the entrepreneurial ecosystem surrounding early-stage start-ups include: Regional and Rural Entrepreneurs/Rural Business Founders, Troy Haines, The Australian Government (Federal and State), and Internet and Phone Providers.

The main stakeholder that is in a position to intervene with the 'regional entrepreneurial ecosystem' would be Troy Haines who has been able "to develop the Far North Queensland startup and innovation ecosystem, at the heart of which lies theSPACE Cairns" (Haines, 2016) With knowledge in developing start-up ecosystems, he would be invaluable to gain insights about the regional ecosystems, and what they need to thrive. He would be the head of this not-for-profit with a support team of experienced innovation experts from across the country.

Another stakeholder that would be crucial in this proposal would be founders who originated from regional and rural areas. These include people like Nicola Rivett, Donna Carrier, Tori Kopke and many more. These people have a background in building a start up and a wealth of knowledge, but more importantly they have a knowledge and connection to the regional communities that they come from.

The Australian Government on both levels would be a key stake holder as they are able to provide information and money in the form of grants. The top three most accessible grants according to Startup Muster's 2018 Report were:

1. R&D Tax Incentive
2. MVP Grant
3. Accelerating Commercialisation

Funding for this would be coming from grants as per above and also sponsors. These sponsors are also stakeholders within this proposal, they will most likely be corporate companies that see the value of supporting innovation within regional areas of Australia. Telcos like Optus and Telstra would likely be optimal sponsors as they would be able to provide their services as well as monetary inputs.

The proposal would start with some of the bigger regional areas as they have slight advantages in population, transport, and educational facilities. The reason we would be starting in these bigger areas is because there may already a small ecosystem that could be built off as opposed to starting from scratch, eventually the smaller regional towns will be connected with the same services.

It is likely that this initial set up will take a minimum of five years to build up the ecosystems and create a developing web of connections across Australia. Once the initial "Hubs" are set up there will be more visible and accessible opportunities for people out in regional and rural Australia. As the ten-year mark is reached it would be ideal that there is a strong ecosystem built between many regional towns and cities, and the success of this not-for-profit invites more people to become part of the entrepreneurial community across Australia.

As the government works with all the major stakeholders within the ecosystem, it will continue to solidify the government as an integral and relevant actor within the ecosystem within obstructing the natural state of the free market to a disadvantageous extent. The trade-off for stakeholder participation is immense exposure for these stakeholders and in return, relationship with the government and an awareness of the onus each actor has to assist new founders as much as makes sense for each actor, breaking down Australia's prevalence of tall poppy syndrome and adopting some of the values that have contributed to the immense success of the Silicon Valley entrepreneurial ecosystem, fostering a ubiquitous 'win-win' paradigm that transforms the ability for new founders to enter and thrive within the national ecosystem.

Activators:

Government receives a bolstered and more educated start-up community in all states. Broader reach means that their funding is strengthening the knowledge of multiple entrepreneurs which may provide a greater return on investment than grant funding into one idea.

Stakeholders:

Entrepreneurs receive a kick start to their start up process. The advice is personal and can direct them on their best next steps.

Start-up hubs (Incubators, Accelerators, Talent) are given crucial networking opportunities and referrals to entrepreneurs who would've otherwise avoided the ecosystem.

Value:

The value that the third leverage proposal will generate for the stakeholders will not be immediate monetary value that stakeholders will often look to as a signifier of success. However, the value that will be created through the building of stronger networks and connections within the regional entrepreneurial ecosystem nationally and state-wide. The government will benefit greatly from this intervention, as enabling the ideas and local information will result in more start-ups being created to solve problems that might otherwise be overlooked. There is also the value of potential job creation that comes with the growth of these entrepreneurial ventures as they expand from their local region all the way across Australia.

The Start-up founders will also generate value from working with these start-ups by potentially being able to partner up with them and help develop the ideas of the new entrepreneurs from regional areas. This could also result in expansion of the founders own personal network as they become more connected with different industries and sectors, building on their own personal connections and business possibilities.

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